

FAIR workflow guide

Data access

Publish data in a repository with a specified license - or link to original data source.

Compute environment

Create an image (e.g. Docker image) of your environment and make it available for reuse.

Workflow engine

Manage multiple tasks (serial or parallel) with different environments in a reproducible manner.

Digital Research Product

Store all information by linking to data, metadata, software, publications, etc. in a FAIR way.

Fact sheet

- Examples for creating workflows using the PUNCH4NFDI resources and the analysis platform REANA are available under:
https://gitlab-p4n.aip.de/punch_public/reana/tutorials
 - REANA is an open source software, provided by CERN. <https://docs.reana.io/>
 - Many other workflow management systems exist, such as Dirac <http://diracgrid.org/>
- Data should be published as open as possible. This is even more important for the metadata.
- When choosing a license for data, metadata or software, take into account the regulations by your institution.
- Kreuzer, T. Open Content – Navigating Creative Commons Licenses. Deutsche UNESCO-Kommission e. V. (2024). https://www.unesco.de/assets/dokumente/Kommunikation/01_Kommunikation_allgemein/Open-Content_Dez_2024.pdf
- A registry for Digital Research Products is provided by PUNCH4NFDI under <https://rpr-p4n.aip.de/>
- PUNCH4NFDI services might require registration to the PUNCH-AAI, a group in the Helmholtz ID, see <https://results.punch4nfdi.de/?md=/docs/Documents/punch-aii.md>

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